

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL SUPPORT FOR EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

Khudayberdiev Abdurashid Abdirasulovich

Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of
Uzbekistan

Associate Professor of the Department of Administrative Law,
Doctor of Philosophy in Law (PhD), Associate Professor

Ochilov Bokhodir Khudoyberdievich

Head of the Educational Work Department of the 13th Penitentiary
Institution of the first regional area of the Main Directorate for the
Execution of Sentences under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13917846>

Abstract: The article discusses issues of developing the activities of the structure operating in the educational direction in the educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, as well as addressing some shortcomings in this area.

Keywords: Individual education, information and propaganda, public engagement, preventive measures, education and upbringing, patriotism.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5005 dated April 10, 2017, aimed at radically increasing the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies and ensuring reliable protection of citizens' rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, one of the most important directions for reforming the system of internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the task of transforming them into a socially oriented professional structure that provides timely and high-quality assistance to the population, where each employee considers "Serving the interests of the people" as their professional duty [1]. Therefore, the requirements for employees of internal affairs bodies demand that they be masters of their craft, adaptable to social conditions, and possess the qualities of being specialists in their profession.

As the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted, ..."today we are facing the scourge of ignorance in the spheres of economy, education, healthcare, justice, culture, in all aspects of our lives, and this evil is like shackles on our hands and feet. Without being freed from these shackles, there can be no talk of progress and development." [2]

The following types of educational work are utilized in the educational structures of the Ministry of Internal Affairs' educational institutions:

Individual upbringing - Should be conducted regularly and purposefully with personnel and recorded in the journal of individual educational work.

Information and propaganda - Involves conveying information necessary for an employee's official duties, as well as reforms being implemented by the state.

Public involvement - Engaging public structures operating within the system, such as Veterans and Disciplinary Councils, in the training of employees, and utilizing their capabilities.

Preventive measures - Conducting raids and other simulated activities, as well as analyzing rumors spread among employees and others, to determine necessary measures for preventing negative situations.

"The system of training personnel for law enforcement should be based on the latest approaches, adapting to rapidly changing times and conditions. Young professionals need to develop critical analysis, discipline, integrity, patriotism, initiative, and personal responsibility." [3]

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev of our country stated, "As a person realizes their identity and lineage, a sense of love for the Motherland takes root in their heart and grows. The deeper this root, the more boundless the love for the country where they were born and raised. They believe their destiny is connected to the prosperity of the Motherland." [4]

Today, one of the most urgent tasks for the educational structures of higher educational institutions under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of our republic is to educate all cadets and trainees to be loyal to their region, people, and state. To achieve this, it is necessary to educate trainees and cadets in educational institutions under the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the spirit of "serving the interests of the people."

The education of trainees in the Ministry of Internal Affairs' educational institutions consists of physical, spiritual, and military training. Physical education cultivates the body, education imparts military knowledge and skills, and patriotic education nurtures the spirit.

Popularizing military knowledge inherited from our ancestors and teaching the secrets of military art are also effective factors in the overall professional development of trainees studying in educational institutions within the Ministry of Internal Affairs system, fostering their perseverance and courage.

Educational work in the internal affairs bodies' educational structures requires education not only on ideological, social, economic, moral, and ideological grounds but also as a socio-political direction in the process of teaching professional and specialized disciplines.

In the system of educating trainees and cadets of educational institutions, the internal affairs bodies justify and demonstrate pedagogical rules, combat, socio-political, and psychological training, quality indicators in defense construction, and methods and forms of education. They also play an important role in uniting the collective in higher educational institutions.

It should be noted that today the system of educating students and cadets in educational institutions of the internal affairs bodies is developing in several directions: first - in the Ministry of Internal Affairs' boarding school, second - in Temurbek schools, third - in the Ministry of Internal Affairs' academic lyceums, fourth - in the Ministry of Internal Affairs' primary preparatory schools, fifth - in the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (full-time education, correspondence education, faculty of professional training, master's programs), and sixth - in special courses at the Ministry of Internal Affairs' Institute for Advanced Training.

The upbringing of trainees in educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system consists of professional and specialized training, intellectual and physical development, as well as psychological training.

The system of training trainees and cadets in educational structures of educational institutions of internal affairs bodies is their acquisition of knowledge and skills related to their profession in a clear and necessary volume. Intellectual and physical development

consists of analyzing, defining, and summarizing the skills of trainees. This further enhances the psychological and physical qualities necessary for the formation of trainees as highly qualified personnel, as well as their professional activity.

The upbringing of trainees and cadets in the educational structures of educational institutions of internal affairs bodies shows the positive formation of trainees and cadets in the process of education and upbringing, their striving for a goal, emotional attitude towards their profession, their engagement, their inner feelings towards difficulties related to service activities, which correspond to internal will stability. Upbringing arises in the educational process, furthermore, it requires general specialized educational and upbringing activities.

The most important law of career guidance in internal affairs bodies is the professional training of young people. It ensures a connection to a specific type of human activity, shaping the suitability of individuals who have chosen this profession for the military profession. It requires a wide network of higher educational institutions, centers, courses, schools and others under the Ministry of Internal Affairs, a significant material and technical base, the application of all the achievements of science and culture, the availability of the necessary number of highly qualified teaching staff, professional development, the availability of inter-university forms and methods, meetings, seminars, scientific and technical conferences, reading, exercises, games, etc., a developed network of publishing activities, the development of scientific work, and the acquisition of socio-political information.

Indeed, without studying the experience of veterans, it is impossible to cultivate the upbringing of listeners and cadets and instill in their minds the idea of serving the people. After all, the main goal is to educate not only specialists who can use professional and specialized knowledge and skills, but also a specialist who is loyal to his country and serves the people in any situation.

From this perspective, the reform of the system of education and upbringing of trainees and cadets in the educational structures of the Ministry of Internal Affairs educational institutions is changing many outdated ideas and rules, that is, forming a new, scientifically sound system, taking into account the experience of developed countries.

Through many years of experience, various forms and methods have been developed for selecting employees of internal affairs bodies based on their moral and psychological qualities, including: first, the collection and study of questionnaire data about a person; familiarization with descriptions, psychological analysis of biographies, individual interviews, the method of independent descriptions, and others.

Recently, "deep psychology" methods - project tests - have been used to identify certain aspects of personality: Cattell, Leongard (accentuation), Potyomkina (SOL), D. Telar (anxiety scale), and others. The second method includes the mental structures acquired by the individual: knowledge, skills, abilities, and habits. Such a traditional form of selection in educational institutions under the Ministry of Internal Affairs is the results of the competition, entrance exams, exams in law enforcement departments and specialties, qualification level. Thirdly, the content is made up of aspects of psychomotor skills, emotions, which depend on the individual characteristics of mental processes (feelings, perception, imagination, attention, thinking). Tests emerge as a means of determining professional suitability based on individual psychological characteristics. Fourthly, innate traits reflect a set of organic properties that are prioritized over acquired ones. It includes the type of nervous system, needs, gender, age, and other characteristics that manifest in temperament.

An analysis of the educational work carried out with listeners and cadets in the educational structures of educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs shows some problems in this regard.

measures aimed at instilling in the minds of the younger generation a sense of loyalty to the Motherland and involvement in its fate, forming ideological immunity against the negative influence of alien ideas and views, are not yielding sufficient results.

In the educational structures of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, measures related to the upbringing of cadets and trainees, the protection of human rights and their deep integration into the consciousness of young people should be launched in general education schools. After all, great attention should be paid to patriotic education in lyceums, colleges, and higher educational institutions.

The role and significance of upbringing of listeners and cadets in the educational process is increasing in connection with the rapid development of science and technology in our country. Because the sharp increase in activity specialties, in turn, requires an increase in the level of general education of young people hired and enrolled in internal affairs bodies, an increase in their understanding and skills in using new methods of working with people. This requires strengthening the responsibility of specialists training for internal affairs bodies.

For internal affairs bodies, personnel upbringing is a complex process that includes both objective (the influence of the surrounding environment, natural phenomena, etc.) and subjective (conscious and purposeful activities of individuals and public organizations). The task of educators is to maximize the use of these factors in the development of a harmoniously developed individual.

Subjective factors play an important role in the upbringing of the younger generation. It is known that if we equip students and cadets of educational institutions under the Ministry of Internal Affairs with new, modern foundations of science, we can create conditions for their comprehensive development, awakening in them a high consciousness, a sense of patriotism, loyalty to the Motherland.

Therefore, in the upbringing of listeners and cadets, it is necessary not only to familiarize them with modern knowledge and develop skills in working with people; but also to constantly cultivate physical culture and love for the profession. It also involves being modest, honest, disciplined, setting an example in education, work, and life, and most importantly, being loyal to the country, patriotic, patient, and steadfast, overcoming any difficulties, helping comrades in the most difficult moments, and teaching them to unconditionally obey the commands of leaders.

The era demands that we pay serious attention to the organization and improvement of the educational process, the training of national personnel. This process should meet the most modern requirements, take into account the latest scientific achievements, experience in communication with people, including foreign experience.

The upbringing and awareness of listeners and cadets largely depends on the educational work carried out at school. As Russian scholar I. M. Sechenov noted, "spiritual action, no matter how simple, is the result of a person's growth throughout the past and present."

In conclusion, it should be noted that to overcome the aforementioned problems and further improve the work on raising the younger generation, teachers and mentors themselves

should embody similar qualities in the formation of legal awareness and worldview, a sense of service to the people among listeners and cadets.

References:

- 1.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ички ишлар органларининг фаолияти самарадорлигини тубдан ошириш, жамоат тартибини, фуқаролар ҳуқуқлари, эркинликлари ва қонуний манфаатларини ишончли ҳимоя қилишни таъминлашда уларнинг масъулиятини кучайтириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги 5005-сонли Фармони Т., 2017 йил 10 апрель.
- 2.Президентимиз Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг 2017 йил 3 август куни мамлакатимиз ижодкор зиёлилари билан учрашувда сўзлаган нутқидан.
- 3.Қонун устувор, адолат барқарор бўлса, жиноятчиликка ўрин қолмайди // [Электрон манба]. – URL: [https:// president. uz/uz/ lists/view/2237](https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/2237) – (мурожаат этилган сана – 2024.09.04).
- 4.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси. – Халқ сўзи. – 2018.
- 5.Юсупов Э. Ю. Ёшлар ўртасида ватанпарварлик тарбиясини амалга ошириш йўллари (илмий-услубий тавсиялар). – Т.: Университет, 1996. – 21-б.
- 6.Абдурасулов О.А., Қурбонов Р.Ю. Ёшларни замонавий техника асослари билан таништиришда ҳарбий ватанпарварлик ва миллий истиқлол ғоясининг роли //Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қуролли Кучларининг тарихи, бугуни ва келажаги: Республика илмий-амалий анжумани материаллари. – Тошкент: ЎР МВ, 2005. – Б. 86-90.
- 7.Сеченов И.М. Избранные философские и психологические произведения. – М.: Мысль, 2013. – С. 311.
- 8.Ахмедова С.Т. Ички ишлар органлари тизимидаги маъмурий-ҳуқуқий ислохотлар инсон кадрлари учун //Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 10 Special Issue. – С. 15-19.
- 9.Ахмедова С.Т., Охунов З.М. Особенности применения административных взысканий за управление автотранспортом в состоянии опьянения //Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 6. – С. 48-54.
- 10.Ахмедова С.Т. К вопросу об освидетельствовании на состояние опьянения водителей транспортных средств //Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. Special Issue 6. – С. 55-59.
- 11.Ахмедова С.Т. Об актуальных проблемах совершенствования административного законодательства Республики Узбекистан. – 2022.
- 12.Ахмедова С.Т., Янгибаев А. К. Особенности деятельности инспекторов профилактики по законодательству республики узбекистан features of the activities of prevention inspectors under the legislation of the republic of Uzbekistan //Административно-правовое регулирование правоохранительной деятельности: теория и практика. – 2022. – С. 32-37.
- 13.Маматкулов Т.Б., Ахмедова С.Т. Аспекты взаимодействия инспекторов профилактики с махаллэй в охране общественного порядка и обеспечении безопасности граждан (на примере узбекистана) aspects of interaction of prevention inspectors with //редакционно-издательским советом Краснодарского университета

МВД России Редакционная коллегия: КД Рыдченко, кандидат юридических наук, доцент (председатель). – С. 505.

